

EMPAIA App Interface: An open and vendor-neutral interface for AI applications in pathology

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ABSTRACT

Background and objective: Artificial intelligence (AI) apps hold great potential to make pathological diagnoses more accurate and time efficient. Widespread use of AI in pathology is hampered by interface incompatibilities between pathology software. We studied the existing interfaces in order to develop the EMPAIA App Interface, an open standard for the integration of pathology AI apps.

Methods: The EMPAIA App Interface relies on widely-used web communication protocols and containerization. It consists of three parts: A standardized format to describe the semantics of an app, a mechanism to deploy and execute apps in computing environments, and a web API through which apps can exchange data with a host application.

Results: Five commercial AI app manufacturers successfully adapted their products to the EMPAIA App Interface and helped improve it with their feedback. Open source tools facilitate the adoption of the interface by providing reusable data access and scheduling functionality and enabling automatic validation of app compliance.

Conclusions: Existing AI apps and pathology software can be adapted to the EMPAIA App Interface with little effort. It is a viable alternative to the proprietary interfaces of current software. If enough vendors join in, the EMPAIA App Interface can help to advance the use of AI in pathology.

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1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a key driver for the digitization of pathology, as it holds great potential to make pathological diagnoses more accurate, reproducible and time efficient [1,2]. AI applications in pathology, also referred to as "apps", utilize modern machine learning techniques to extract diagnostic information from tissue images. Tissue images are captured using specialized slide-

scanner hardware that digitizes tissue sections at microscopic resolution. This results in very large whole slide images (WSIs) that are several gigapixels in size. Diagnostic information may be diagnostic scores, such as the percentage of certain cells, a disease grade, or the presence of an abnormality. It may also be annotations of relevant cell or tissue areas, such as tumor tissue.

Pathology AI apps are generally triggered from a digital pathology workstation [3]. A typical workstation provides a central user interface for pathologists to examine WSIs, access patient data and enter diagnostic results. WSIs can be explored by zooming and panning, similar to online mapping software, and the user can annotate or take measurements of relevant structures (Fig. 1). Many pathology workstations give users the ability to select AI apps to

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Fig. 1. Screenshot of a prototypical web viewer contained in the EMPAIA App Test Suite [4] that allows users to explore WSIs and to assess annotations produced by AI apps. Similar viewers are provided by most pathology workstations.

run and enter additional parameters, such as regions of interest (ROI). After running the AI app, the resulting diagnostic scores or annotations are received back and displayed by the workstation. Alternatively, some AI apps offer their own user interface for setting algorithm parameters and visualizing results.

A growing number of pathology workstation software is capable of integrating AI apps. This includes both commercial and open-source software [5,6]. To exploit the full potential of AI, pathologists must be able to use multiple types of apps for a variety of diagnostic tasks and from different vendors. Since each workstation has its own way of integrating software extensions, AI developers need to adapt their solutions to each workstation individually. This is a large effort and often requires partnerships with commercial workstation vendors to obtain the necessary interface information [3]. As a result, the existing workstations only allow the use of a small subset of available AI apps, and developers can only offer their solutions to a small subset of customers. Currently, this is a major obstacle to the widespread use of AI in pathology.

In this paper, we describe the EMPAIA App Interface, a unified vendor-agnostic interface for integrating AI apps into pathology workstations. The interface was developed in the context of the EMPAIA project (Ecosystem for Pathology Diagnostics with AI Assistance) [7] in collaboration with several commercial AI app manufacturers. We begin by summarizing the interfaces of existing pathology workstations that were considered in the development of the EMPAIA App Interface. We then provide a specification with examples and describe how pathology workstations and AI apps can adopt the EMPAIA App Interface with little effort. Finally, we discuss its advantages compared to the existing interfaces and give an outlook on future developments.

1.1. Related work

We studied the existing interfaces for integrating AI apps into pathology workstations, based on publicly available information

[8–10] and information provided to us by commercial software manufacturers. We considered both workstations for pathologists, which have typical image-centric user interfaces as described above [5,6], and systems for biomedical researchers, which are optimized for flexibility and allow their users to create complex workflows of multiple AI apps [10]. While some software systems refer to AI applications as modules, extensions, or tools, we refer to them all as “apps”.

1.1.1. Execution

The existing interfaces generally support one or more of the following integration options for AI apps: standalone software, shared libraries, or web services. Standalone software typically runs on the same machine as a pathology workstation and provides its own user interface. Shared libraries must be implemented in the development platform of the host software (e.g., Java or .NET). They are usually deeply integrated into the user interface of the pathology workstation [9]. Web services run either locally or remotely on optimized hardware, which can be particularly advantageous with regard to the high computing requirements of AI apps. They are either integrated into the user interface of the pathology workstation or provide their own. Modern pathology workstations often expect AI apps to be packaged as software containers [8,10], such as Docker [11]. This greatly facilitates automated deployment within computing clusters and allows AI apps to be implemented on any development platform.

AI apps either must be started independently or are executed on demand by the pathology workstation. Independent execution is a viable option for web services, as it allows them to be operated without the requirement of a particular workstation instance [8]. Independently executed AI app services must provide an external interface (e.g., HTTP endpoints) that can be invoked by pathology workstations to trigger an analysis. Demand driven execution enables the pathology workstation to manage AI apps and reduces maintenance effort. AI apps implemented as

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of an AI app in pathology with typical input and output parameters.

shared libraries or packaged as software containers are often executed on demand [8,9]. They must be executable according to an application programming interface (API) or standardized command line interface (CLI) respectively, both specified by the host application.

Registration of AI apps in pathology workstations must either be done explicitly [10] or it happens in an auto-discovery process, e.g., by searching for specific shared libraries [9]. AI apps must be self-descriptive so that their host application can present and run them. Typical information that must be provided includes their name, logo and field of application, input and output data details, and an execution command or URL. Self-descriptiveness is either achieved by supplying a descriptor file, often in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format [8,10], or by implementing an API to be called by the host application.

1.1.2. Data exchange

Pathology AI apps generally have similar types of input and output data. Input data includes algorithm parameters, annotations of relevant image areas (incl. ROIs), and the images to process. Input images are accompanied by metadata, such as their resolution, and color model, which are essential for running the app. Output data includes diagnostic scores or annotations of identified cellular or tissue structures (Fig. 2).

It is common for pathology workstations to offer an API through which apps can query input data and return output data. Apps implemented as shared libraries are usually provided with platform-dependent APIs [9], while standalone software and web services are provided with web APIs [8]. Alternatively, some systems transfer input data when an analysis is triggered, e.g., as parameters to the execution command [10] or API endpoint. In this case, complex input data or output data, such as images or annotations, are sometimes exchanged by writing files to storage locations with mutual access [10].

In the existing interfaces for AI apps, parameters and diagnostic scores are typically exchanged as simple numbers or strings that relate to ROIs or the entire image. Annotations are mostly represented as geometric shapes, such as points, rectangles or polygons, and sometimes as binary mask [8].

The distinction between file-based and API-based access is particularly important when accessing input images. Today, there is a multitude of proprietary WSI file formats. File-based access en-

ables AI apps to take full advantage of individual file format features. API-based access, on the other hand, reduces the development effort for AI apps because no specific file access functionality needs to be implemented. Due to the enormous size of WSIs, file-based access only works if AI apps have efficient random access to the image files. API-based access usually enables AI apps to query individual subregions of WSIs at specific resolutions so that only small subregions of images are transferred [8]. This makes it better suited for AI apps running remotely.

2. Methods

We considered the similarities and differences, as well as the strengths and weaknesses of the existing interfaces, in order to develop a general interface for AI apps in pathology. The result is the EMPAIA App Interface. This interface relies on web communication protocols and containerization and consists of three parts: The EMPAIA App Description, the EMPAIA App Runtime Specification, and the EMPAIA App API. The following sections give a brief overview of the EMPAIA App Interface. More information and the complete specification can be found in the EMPAIA App Developer Documentation [12].

2.1. EMPAIA App Description

The EMPAIA App Description (EAD) is a standardized format for describing the semantics of an app. Every app must be accompanied by an EAD, so that pathology workstations can present suitable apps for a given usage context and provide input and process output data in an appropriate manner. The EAD summarizes the name, a human-readable description, and the input and output parameters of an app. It may also define configuration options and a taxonomy of class names. Every EAD must contain a namespace declaration. Parameter names or class names defined in an EAD are prefixed with this namespace to make them globally unique identifiers. EADs are defined in JSON format (Fig. 3) and need to comply with the EAD schema [12].

An app can receive multiple input parameters and return multiple output parameters. Both can have references to other parameters. While input parameters may only reference input parameters, output parameters may reference both input and output parameters. Each parameter must be of one of the following data types.

2.1.1. Whole slide image

Parameters of type *wsi* represent metadata associated with a whole slide image, such as its resolution, pyramid levels, channel depth and pixel size, in a vendor-neutral manner. WSI parameters can contain an identifier for querying the actual image data from the EMPAIA App API. Currently, this type can only be used for input parameters.

2.1.2. Annotations

Annotations are geometrical objects that are created either manually by the user or programmatically by an app. They can be of type *point*, *line*, *arrow*, *rectangle*, *polygon*, or *circle*. Freehand drawings made with interactive tools are represented as polygons. Annotations always contain a reference to the corresponding WSI. Input annotations may contain a property *classes* with a list of class identifiers. This is interpreted as a constraint, that is, the app expects the input annotation to have a semantic meaning of one of the specified class identifiers (Fig. 3).

2.1.3. Primitives

Primitive parameters represent simple values such as *integer*, *float*, *string*, or *boolean*. They may optionally contain a name and

```

{
  "$schema": "https://developer.empaia.org/schema/ead-app-schema-draft-3.json",
  "name": "Example App 1",
  "namespace": "org.empaia.example_vendor.example_app_1.v1",
  "description": "Counts cells for a given rectangular WSI region",
  "inputs": {
    "wsi": { "type": "wsi" },
    "region_of_interest": {
      "type": "rectangle",
      "reference": "inputs.wsi",
      "classes": [ "org.empaia.global.v1.classes.roi" ]
    }
  },
  "outputs": {
    "cell_count": {
      "type": "integer",
      "reference": "inputs.region_of_interest"
    }
  }
}

```

Fig. 3. EAD of an app which expects a WSI and a region of interest as input parameters and which returns the calculated cell count within that ROI as an output parameter.

description. For numerical input data types, it is possible to provide min and max values. Primitive parameters may reference a WSI or an annotation to enable context-related information. For example, an output parameter *tumor_cell_count* could reference a *rectangle* annotation from which it was derived.

2.1.4. Class

Parameters of type *class* provide class identifiers for a referenced input or output annotation. A typical use case is the return of classification results for certain input annotations (Fig. 4).

2.1.5. Collection

A parameter of type *collection* is a list of variable size of elements of one type. For example, an app could output a collection of point annotations of identified cells. Collections can be nested to any depth.

Class identifiers must either be a standard class identifier or defined in a custom class taxonomy. The standard class identifiers are defined in the EAD specification [12]. For example, the standard class identifier *org.empaia.global.v1.classes.roi* represents a region of interest. Custom class taxonomies are defined in the *classes* section of an EAD (Fig. 4). This section contains a set of class names which can be nested hierarchically to indicate superclass and subclass relations.

2.2. EMPAIA App Runtime Specification

The EMPAIA App Runtime Specification is a standardized mechanism to deploy and execute apps. It stipulates that apps are deployed as container images compliant with the Open Container Initiative's (OCI) image specification [13], such as Docker container images [11]. It also requires that app instances created from these images are provided with the following three environment variables in order to be able to communicate with the App API.

EMPAIA_APP_API: The URL of the EMPAIA App API that the app should use to request input data and return output data. By customizing this URL, apps can be flexibly mapped to different app services in distributed computing environments.

EMPAIA_JOB_ID: An identifier of the application instance. Apps must send the job ID with each API request in order to enable the workstation providing the App API to identify the app and to deliver input data and process output data according to its EAD.

EMPAIA_TOKEN: A JSON Web Token (JWT) [14] that is used by apps to obtain authorized access to the App API. It is created and cryptographically signed by the workstation.

2.3. EMPAIA App API

The EMPAIA App API must be provided by workstations to enable apps to exchange input and output data and to signal the completion of their analysis. It follows the Representational State Transfer (REST) paradigm [15] and consists of a set of URL endpoints (Table 1). Apps can retrieve input data or post output data to these endpoints using standard HTTP request methods [16]. For authorized requests, the JWT token passed in the environment variable *EMPAIA_TOKEN* needs to be specified in the HTTP *Authorization* Header using the Bearer schema [17].

Input and output data are exchanged as JSON documents. There is an OpenAPI specification [18] that describes how the different EAD parameter types are encoded as JSON data structures [12]. Fig. 5 shows an exemplary point annotation in JSON format.

The enormous size of WSI makes it impractical to process them as a whole. To enable quick access to different resolutions, WSIs are stored as image pyramids, with higher levels containing an increasingly smaller downsampled version of the original image. Each level is stored as a lattice of tiles that can be loaded independently. The EMPAIA App interface allows apps to take advantage of the pyramidal and tiled storage of WSI, regardless of the particular WSI file format. Via the */regions* and */tiles* endpoints, apps can efficiently request only relevant image regions at particular resolutions. Image metadata, such as the ID or the widths and heights of the pyramid levels can be requested via the */inputs* endpoint. Image regions or tiles are returned as PNG images by default. It is possible to request other image formats by specifying a query parameter.

```

{
  "$schema": "https://developer.empaia.org/schema/ead-app-schema-draft-3.json",
  "name": "Example App 2",
  "namespace": "org.empaia.example_vendor.example_app_2.v1",
  "description": "Classifies cells as tumorous or non tumorous",
  "classes": {
    "tumor": { "name": "Tumor" },
    "non_tumor": { "name": "Non tumor" }
  },
  "inputs": {
    "wsi": { "type": "wsi" },
    "cells": {
      "type": "collection",
      "items": { "type": "point", "reference": "inputs.wsi" }
    }
  },
  "outputs": {
    "classification": {
      "type": "collection",
      "items": {
        "type": "class",
        "reference": "inputs.cells.items"
      }
    }
  }
}

```

Fig. 4. EAD of an app that expects a WSI and a collection of cell locations within that WSI as input parameters and that returns a collection of classifications as an output parameter, identifying the cell locations as either tumor or non-tumor.

```

{
  "id": "b10648a7-340d-43fc-a2d9-4d91cc86f33f",
  "name": "Nucleus",
  "reference_id": "7b617060-7fb8-4387-94a9-99f71530084e",
  "reference_type": "wsi",
  "npp_created": 499,
  "type": "point",
  "coordinates": [7483, 12144],
  "creator_id": "b10648a7-340d-43fc-a2d9-4d91cc86f33f",
  "creator_type": "job",
  "created_at": "1598611645",
  "updated_at": "1598611645"
}

```

Fig. 5. Example JSON representation of a point annotation in a referenced WSI.

2.4. Implementation

2.4.1. Implementation by pathology workstations

To enable a pathology workstation to run EMPAIA App Interface compliant apps, it must execute them according to the EMPAIA App Runtime Specification and implement the EMPAIA App API for data exchange.

A typical pathology workstation might offer a context menu showing all apps that may be run with the current image and input parameters by evaluation of the respective EADs. Once the user selects an app for execution, the workstation starts a new job, that is, a new instance of the app with a given set of input parameters. The execution of a job corresponds to the execution of the container image of an app. At startup, the three environment variables defined by the EMPAIA App Runtime Specification must be specified: *EMPAIA_APP_API*, *EMPAIA_JOB_ID*, and *EMPAIA_TOKEN*, where

the API parameter must contain the URL to the implementation of the EMPAIA App API and the job ID and token values must be managed by the workstation.

Running containers on a machine other than the one requesting their execution is easily possible by contacting a remote container engine, e.g., through the Docker command line interface. For more advanced scheduling tasks, a container orchestration framework such as Kubernetes [19] can be used. The pathology workstation requesting the execution of an app must set up what is called a “Pod”. This is a formal specification of what to run with which parameters on a given compute cluster. Any hardware associated with a compute cluster is then managed by the orchestration framework and the pathology workstation only needs to interact with the Kubernetes Control Plane API.

To enable apps to query input and return output parameters, a pathology workstation must implement the EMPAIA App API (Fig. 6). When AI apps invoke the respective endpoints, they authenticate their requests with the web token and job ID they received at startup (as HTTP header and URL parameter, respectively). They also specify an identifier for the respective input or output parameter which is defined in the app’s EAD. For each job, pathology workstations must maintain a mapping between the identifiers of the data structures they use internally and the identifiers used by the respective apps.

Pathology workstations are responsible for converting internal representations of input data (such as ROIs) to a matching EMPAIA JSON data type. Conversely, they are also responsible for converting output data from apps into suitable internal representations. For image data, pathology workstations must be able to provide arbitrary regions of their managed whole-slide images and transfer them in the data formats defined by the EMPAIA App API.

Table 1

Overview of the RESTful HTTP endpoints of the EMPAIA App API. Path parameters are indicated by curly brackets. The prefix */v0* defines the API version. The *job_id* is an identifier of the current application instance.

HTTP Method	URI	Description
GET	<i>/v0/{job_id}/configuration</i>	Retrieves app specific configuration options
GET	<i>/v0/{job_id}/inputs/{input_parameter}</i>	Retrieves specific input data for the given <i>input_parameter</i> in the EAD.
GET	<i>/v0/{job_id}/regions/{wsi_id}/level/{level}/start/{start_x}/{start_y}/size/{size_x}/{size_y}</i>	Retrieves image data of a specific WSI region using the corresponding <i>wsi_id</i> (retrieved via the above <i>/inputs</i> endpoint), a zoom <i>level</i> , <i>start_x/y</i> coordinates and the region's <i>size_x/y</i> in pixels.
GET	<i>/v0/{job_id}/tiles/{wsi_id}/level/{level}/position/{tile_x}/{tile_y}</i>	Retrieves image data of a specific WSI tile using the corresponding <i>wsi_id</i> (retrieved via the above <i>/inputs</i> endpoint), a zoom <i>level</i> , and <i>tile_x/y</i> index positions.
PUT	<i>/v0/{job_id}/collections/{collection_id}/query[?skip={offset}&limit={limit}]</i>	Retrieves items from a potentially large collection. Filter criteria are part of the request's body and query parameters <i>skip</i> and <i>limit</i> allow pagination.
POST	<i>/v0/{job_id}/outputs/{output_parameter}</i>	Posts specific output data for the given <i>output_parameter</i> in the EAD.
POST	<i>/v0/{job_id}/collections/{collection_id}/items</i>	Extends a specific collection with the given <i>collection_id</i> with items.
PUT	<i>/v0/{job_id}/finalize</i>	Finalizes the current job which will mark the processing as complete.

2.4.2. EMPAIA Reference Implementation

We have developed the EMPAIA Reference Implementation to facilitate the adoption of the EMPAIA App Interface. The Reference Implementation is independent of any pathology workstation and released as open source under the commercial friendly MIT license (<https://gitlab.com/empaia/services>). To simplify subsequent use in medical devices, the Reference Implementation is developed ac-

ording to professional software development practices and in a test-driven way.

The Reference Implementation is a set of reusable microservices using a modern technology stack with Python at its foundation. Several subservices specialize in exchanging input and output data. For instance, there is a WSI service, providing region and tile endpoints for different WSI file formats, including Aperio

Fig. 6. Interaction between pathology workstations and AI apps via the EMPAIA App Runtime Specification and EMPAIA App API.

Fig. 7. Pathology workstations can leverage reusable microservices from the EMPAIA Reference Implementation to implement the EMPAIA App Interface.

(* .svs), Hamamatsu (*.ndpi), Philips (*.iSyntax), 3DHitech (*.mrxs), Generic tiff (*.tif/*.tiff), and OME-TIF (*.ome.tif). There is also an annotation service for storing and retrieving image annotations in the described JSON data type format. Other services specialize in starting and managing jobs. The job execution service, for example, provides HTTP endpoints for executing apps by specifying parameters and an app identifier. Upon invocation, it pulls the given container image from a configured registry and runs the app with the given parametrization. There is also a job service which maps identifiers in the EAD of apps and the internal data storage system. Finally, there is an app service providing the HTTP endpoints of the EMPAIA App API. This app service utilizes the other services through a central gateway called Medical Data Service. The services provided by the reference implementation conform to the OAuth 2.0 Authorization Framework [20] and make use of asynchronous I/O operations to allow for parallel processing of many requests. Manufacturers of pathology workstations are free to use any subset of these services and implement the remaining services themselves to address specific requirements (Fig. 7).

2.4.3. Implementation by AI apps

In order to make an AI app compliant with the EMPAIA App Interface, it has to be accompanied by an EAD, be containerized and executable according to the EMPAIA App Runtime Specification, and it must exchange input and output data according to the EMPAIA App API. Apps can be implemented in virtually any programming language and software platform. Fig. 8 shows the source code of an exemplary Python app that is described by the EAD shown in Fig. 3.

The EMPAIA developer documentation contains several tutorials on implementing the EMPAIA App Interface [12]. Each tutorial describes a sample app, including its App API implementation, EAD, and Docker file. The corresponding source code is released as open source. Among other things, the sample apps demonstrate how to map analysis results to input ROIs, or how to output large collections of classified geometric annotations. While the sample apps are for illustrative purposes only, the EMPAIA team has also published an open-source EMPAIA-compliant app that performs an actual image analysis task [21]. The app uses an AI-based inference model that automatically detects and segments glomeruli in WSI of kidney sections.

We provide the open-source EMPAIA App Test Suite [4] to verify the compliance of an app with the EMPAIA App Interface in an automated way. The test suite is operated via a command line interface. To check a particular app, the user must specify its EAD

and container image, as well as the input data. Afterwards, a detailed report of the app's execution, including any errors, is displayed and the output data of the app is visualized in a bundled web viewer (Fig. 1). The EMPAIA App Test Suite itself is written in Python and it integrates several services of the EMPAIA Reference Implementation via the docker python interface.

3. Results

Five AI app manufacturers offering different types of commercial AI products for pathology were invited to adapt one of their solutions to the EMPAIA App Interface (see Acknowledgement). The manufacturers were provided with preliminary releases of the EMPAIA developer documentation, including the interface specification and implementation tutorials, and the EMPAIA App Test Suite. A support channel was set up for the manufacturers to ask questions and provide feedback to the EMPAIA team. Over a six-month period, the manufacturers received updated versions of the interface specification and the test suite, which had been improved several times based on their feedback. All considered apps were successfully adapted to the final version of the interface.

Of the five apps considered, two dealt with tissue recognition and three with cell recognition tasks. The tissue recognition tasks related to the morphological identification of lung cancer, while the cell recognition tasks related to cell positivity scoring or gene amplification quantification. One cell recognition app worked on fluorescent images, while the others worked on brightfield images. All apps expected one WSI and one or more rectangular or polygonal ROIs as input. Outputs were generally given separately for each ROI. The tissue recognition apps returned the detected tissue regions as polygons, some of which were associated with classes. The cell recognition apps returned the detected cells as collections of polygons or points, some of which were associated with classes or class probabilities. They also returned statistics about the distribution of various cell types in a particular ROI (e.g., number of nuclei, positivity score, gene amplification status).

The app manufacturers required only little assistance in implementing the interface and took most of the technical details from the developer documentation. Some topics needed clarification, such as assigning reference IDs, rendering annotations, or deploying and publishing applications. The corresponding explanations are now included in the documentation. In addition, the manufacturers raised some issues, some of which led to changes in the app interface.

```

import os
import requests

from my_algorithms import cell_count

# Read configured environment variables
APP_API = os.environ["EMPAIA_APP_API"]
JOB_ID = os.environ["EMPAIA_JOB_ID"]
TOKEN = os.environ["EMPAIA_TOKEN"]
HEADERS = {"Authorization": f"Bearer {TOKEN}"}

# Retrieve WSI metadata and ROI
wsi = requests.get(url=f"{APP_API}/v0/{JOB_ID}/inputs/wsi", headers=HEADERS).json()
roi = requests.get(url=f"{APP_API}/v0/{JOB_ID}/inputs/region_of_interest", headers=HEADERS).json()

# Retrieve image data from given ROI
start_x, size_x = roi["upper_left"][0], roi["width"]
start_y, size_y = roi["upper_left"][1], roi["height"]
image_data = requests.get(
    url=f"{APP_API}/v0/{JOB_ID}/regions/{wsi['id']}/level/0/start/{start_x}/{start_y}/size/{size_x}/{size_y}",
    headers=HEADERS
).content

# Invoke algorithmic logic and create integer primitive
cell_count = {
    "name": "Number of Cells",
    "type": "integer",
    "value": cell_count(image_data)
}

# Post this result as corresponding output
requests.post(url=f"{APP_API}/v0/{JOB_ID}/outputs/cell_count", json=cell_count, headers=HEADERS)

# Signal app completed successfully
requests.put(url=f"{APP_API}/v0/{JOB_ID}/finalize", headers=HEADERS)

```

Fig. 8. Python source code of an example app that conforms to the EMPAIA App Runtime Specification and uses the EMPAIA App API.

Several issues related to implementing the EMPAIA App Runtime Specification. One app based on the Microsoft .NET framework had to be ported to the .NET Core framework [22] so that it could be embedded in a container image. For AI apps running independently as web services, individual “adapter apps” had to be created. These adapter apps are invocable and exchange data according to the EMPAIA App Interface and they communicate appropriately with the existing AI app services.

One feature of the EMPAIA App Interface that has only emerged through interaction with manufacturers is the configuration endpoint of the EMPAIA App API (Table 1). This endpoint enables apps to query configuration options for a given execution. Apps must specify the names and types of their possible configuration options in their EAD. The need for the configuration endpoint arose from an AI app that runs independently as a web service and requires authentication via credentials. The configuration endpoint enables pathology workstations to manage app credentials in a secure way (e.g., using a vault service) and to provide them to instances of those apps on request. Later, the configuration endpoint was also used by other app manufacturers, for example to map channel names of certain fluorescence image formats.

Based on requests from the manufacturers, the App Test Suite was enhanced with a flexible command line interface that enables different levels of integration testing. This allows the interface compatibility of apps to be tested without containerization, which shortens development cycles.

The adaptation of an app to the EMPAIA App Interface was considered successful if the app could be run by the app test suite without errors and its output was displayed correctly in the test

suite viewer. In one case, an AI app still had to be adapted for communication via a proxy server. This requirement is now also described in the developer documentation.

4. Discussion

The EMPAIA App Interface is the first interface for AI apps in pathology designed for openness and maximum compatibility with different apps and workstations. The interface specification was developed together with multiple AI app vendors and published openly [12]. Relying on web APIs and containerization, the interface is compatible with AI apps and pathology workstations implemented on any software platform and operating system. Input and output data are exchanged in widely-used open data formats (e.g., JSON, PNG) without the need to support vendor-proprietary image formats. The annotation data types closely match the standardization efforts for WSI annotations developed by DICOM Working Group 26 [23], which facilitates interoperability with other software systems.

Flexibility and efficiency were central goals in the design of the EMPAIA App Interface. Unlike some existing interfaces that require AI apps to run on the same computer as the pathology workstation, EMPAIA-compliant apps can run in distributed computing systems and be flexibly scheduled based on available computing resources. Since apps are embedded in standard OCI containers, the full power of industry-standard orchestration frameworks such as Kubernetes [19] can be leveraged. Communication between AI apps and pathology workstations consumes minimum bandwidth. While other interfaces require copying entire image files to a loca-

tion that can be read by AI apps, in the presented approach only required regions of slide images are transferred via HTTP.

Finally, the EMPAIA App Interface is self-descriptive and easy to adopt by existing software systems. The EAD of EMPAIA-compliant apps provides structured meta information about their input and output data requirements and their parameterization. This allows pathology workstations to present appropriate apps for a given image and to deliver input and process output data in an automated manner. There is extensive developer documentation including a clear specification of the EAD and EMPAIA App API [12]. In addition, the open-source EMPAIA App Test Suite enables automated verification of the compatibility of apps with the EMPAIA App Interface. Both of these factors greatly facilitate the smooth adoption of the interface, as was evident during the adaptation of the AI apps described in the Results section.

4.1. Limitations and future work

The current functionality of the EMPAIA App Interface is sufficient to integrate most existing AI apps for pathology into pathology workstations. However, there are still some limitations and opportunities for improvement. It is our goal to address these issues in future versions of the interface while maintaining backward compatibility.

Most importantly, the current version of the interface does not allow heat maps or other types of images or image-like information to be returned as output data. To enable this, we will follow the standards for image-based annotations currently being developed by other standardization bodies such as DICOM Working Group 26 [23].

Moreover, it is currently impossible to define hardware constraints for apps, such as minimum amount of memory or GPU requirements. Future versions of the EAD should contain a dedicated section for hardware constraints. Ideally, it should be possible to define both minimum and optimum requirements in order to schedule apps and use the available computing resources as efficiently as possible.

For research applications, it is often desirable to define processing workflows from multiple apps, where the outputs of one app are inputs to another. An exemplary use case could be the automated identification of relevant tissue areas with one app and the subsequent quantification of tissue parameters in these areas with another app. The Zeiss Apeer platform demonstrates how the definition of such workflows can work in practice [10]. The structured description of the inputs and outputs of apps in the EAD lays the foundation for the definition of processing workflows. Future versions of the EMPAIA App Interface could be extended to include an explicit schema for defining workflows, and a corresponding workflow execution engine could be provided as part of the EMPAIA Reference Implementation.

4.2. Adoption

Both AI app vendors and pathology workstation vendors can benefit from adopting the EMPAIA App Interface. Vendors of AI apps are usually small companies. Since their market share is too small to be able to specify their own interfaces, they have to adapt their products to the individual interfaces of different workstations. The EMPAIA App Interface allows them to reduce this customization effort and to integrate their products in more workstations.

Vendors of pathology workstation, on the other hand, are often large companies that maintain their own software ecosystems. Offering an exclusive selection of AI apps can be a competitive advantage. That's why workstation vendors have little incentive to open their proprietary interfaces to competitors. Still, it will be difficult for individual workstations to cover the wide range of AI use

cases in pathology. By supporting the EMPAIA App Interface, workstation vendors can expand their AI app offerings and increase their attractiveness for the customer. Since the EMPAIA App Interface is inspired by the proprietary interfaces of existing workstations, it should be straightforward to support both interfaces in parallel.

These benefits, however, only apply if a sufficient number of compliant AI solutions and pathology workstations are available. Five commercial AI app vendors have already successfully adapted their products to the EMPAIA App Interface, and the adaptation of further products is in progress. At the time of writing, compliant apps can only be run in the context of the EMPAIA Reference Implementation. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to get workstation manufacturers to support the interface. To drive adoption of the EMPAIA App Interface, the EMPAIA project is working closely with vendors of pathology software systems to establish the use of EMPAIA-compliant apps in conjunction with their respective software systems at multiple clinical sites [7].

5. Conclusions

The proposed EMPAIA App Interface creates a bridge between AI applications and pathology workstations from different vendors. Since it is open, platform-agnostic, and based on widely-used technologies, most existing software can be adapted to the EMPAIA App Interface with little effort. If enough vendors join in, the interface can catalyze the market for AI applications in pathology. Most importantly, the EMPAIA App Interface can give pathologists access to a wide range of AI algorithms for a variety of applications, helping to improve the quality and efficiency of pathology diagnostics.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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References

- [1] A.V. Parwani, Next generation diagnostic pathology: use of digital pathology and artificial intelligence tools to augment a pathological diagnosis, *Diagn. Pathol.* 14 (2019), doi:10.1186/s13000-019-0921-2.
- [2] M.K.K. Niazi, A.V. Parwani, M.N. Gurcan, Digital pathology and artificial intelligence, *Lancet Oncol.* 20 (2019) e253–e261, doi:10.1016/s1470-2045(19)30154-8.
- [3] A. Homeyer, J. Lotz, L.O. Schwen, N. Weiss, D. Romberg, H. Höfener, et al., Artificial intelligence in pathology: from prototype to product, *J. Pathol. Inform.* 12 (2021), doi:10.4103/jpi.jpi_84_20.
- [4] EMPAIA App Test Suite Repository. 2021. Available from <https://gitlab.com/empaia/integration/empaia-app-test-suite> (Accessed 16 July 2021).
- [5] R. Marée, L. Rollus, B. Stévens, R. Hoyoux, G. Louppe, R. Vandaele, et al., Collaborative analysis of multi-gigapixel imaging data using cytamine, *Bioinformatics* 32 (2016) 1395–1401, doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btw013.
- [6] P. Bankhead, M.B. Loughrey, J.A. Fernández, Y. Dombrowski, D.G. McArt, P.D. Dunne, et al., QuPath: open source software for digital pathology image analysis, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (2017), doi:10.1038/s41598-017-17204-5.
- [7] EMPAIA - Ecosystem for Pathology Diagnostics with AI Assistance. 2021. Available from <https://www.empaia.org/> (Accessed 7 Jun 2021).

- [8] Cytomine ULiège R&D documentation portal. 2021. Available from <https://doc.uliege.cytomine.org/> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [9] QuPath wiki. 2021. Available from <https://github.com/qupath/qupath/wiki> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [10] APEER Docs. 2021. Available from <https://docs.apeer.com/> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [11] D. Merkel, Docker: lightweight linux containers for consistent development and deployment, *Linux J.* 2014 (239) (2014) 2.
- [12] EMPAIA App Developer Documentation. 2021. Available from https://developer.empaia.org/app_developer_docs (Accessed 30 Jun 2021).
- [13] Open Container Initiative - Image Format Specification. 2017. Available from <https://github.com/opencontainers/image-spec/blob/v1.0.1/spec.md> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [14] JSON Web Token - IETF Request for Comments 7519. 2015. Available from <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc7519> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [15] R.T. Fielding, Architectural styles and the design of network-based software architectures, University of California, Irvine, 2000, PhD thesis.
- [16] Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP/1.1): Semantics and Content - IETF Request for Comments 7231. 2014. Available from <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc7231#section-4> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [17] The OAuth 2.0 Authorization Framework: Bearer Token Usage - IETF Request for Comments 6750. 2012. Available from <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6750> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [18] OpenAPI Specification. 2021. Available from <https://spec.openapis.org/oas/v3.1.0> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [19] Kubernetes - production-grade container orchestration. 2021. Available from <https://kubernetes.io/> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [20] 2012. The OAuth 2.0 Authorization Framework - IETF Request for Comments 6749. Available from <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6749> (Accessed 30 Jun 2021).
- [21] EMPAIA Kidney Glomeruli Segmentation App. 2021. Available from <https://gitlab.com/empaia/examples/kidney-glomeruli-segmentation-app> (Accessed 2 Dec 2021).
- [22] Microsoft .NET documentation. 2021. Available from <https://docs.microsoft.com/dotnet/> (Accessed 7 May 2021).
- [23] DICOM WG-26: Pathology. 2019. Available from <https://www.dicomstandard.org/activity/wgs/wg-26> (Accessed 7 May 2021).